

The Motivations of Non-English Major Students: A Case Study at a Private University in Ho Chi Minh City

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ABSTRACT: Motivation is considered as attitudes toward the teacher, students, coursework, curriculum-related activities, and all other elements of the state in which a language is taught. This definition of motivation in language learning emphasizes that it is a complex concept because motivation is not only the cognitive attitude of the learner but also related to many other factors, such as teachers, curriculum, and other elements of the learning environment (Gardner, 1985). This study aims to identify the motivations of second-year non-English major students at a private university in Ho Chi Minh City and the factors that significantly influence their learning motivation. Data were collected from 200 students through a questionnaire, which was developed based on the results of group interviews with 10 students. The research applied a mix-methods approach. The findings indicate that extrinsic motivation strongly influences students' language learning, with factors as job opportunity, learning environment, and teaching method having a positive impact. Based on these findings, the study proposes strategies to leverage extrinsic motivation to enhance students' learning outcomes.

KEYWORDS: motivation, learning motivation, non-English major students, private university.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO), the need to use English in daily work is sustainably high (69%) based on surveys. English, the most utilized foreign language in Vietnam right now, is also a requirement for promotion and salary raises. In addition, according to another statistic from Ethnologue magazine in 2021, English is one of the most widely used languages in the world. Therefore, studying English is essential to a student's academic pathway, regardless of occupation or university.

Lifrieri (2005, p. 4) showed that "when asked about the factors which influence individual levels of success in any activity – such as language learning –most people would certainly mention motivation among them.". According to Tran (2007), students who do not major in English mainly learn English due to external needs, such as pursuing higher education and preparing for future careers. Therefore, it is crucial to identify factors that maintain the motivation of non-English major students in the following years. This helps students meet course requirements effectively and improves their ability to use English in the future work environment.

It is a general challenge for non-major students to keep learning English motivation. In the second year, their motivation is influenced by many internal and external factors. The enthusiasm of the first year is overwhelmed by other concerns, which are causing severe impacts on their motivation. The students often focus more and more on their specialized subjects, which decreases their motivation to learn English.

In addition, the learning environment, teaching methods, and students' perceptions also change significantly in the second year. Many teaching methods are no longer appropriate. The students experienced difficulties and pressure from the specialized topics, which decreased their interest in and motivation for English. Furthermore, the changing learning environment, including the growing up of academic and social activities, causes students to be overwhelmed and have no time or energy to learn English.

Therefore, this study surveys the main factors affecting the motivation to learn English among non-English major students at a university in Ho Chi Minh City. The main goal is to detect and interpret these factors to propose effective solutions that help to maintain their motivation. This research hopes to improve the results of learning English and help the students complete the subject requirements and use English confidently and effectively in their future work.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Definitions

Motivation plays an important role throughout the learning process. There are many different definitions of motivation. Gardner (1985) defined motivation as “Attitudes toward the teacher, students, coursework, curriculum-related activities, and all other elements of the state in which a language is taught.”. This definition of motivation in language learning emphasizes that it is a complex concept because motivation is not only the cognitive attitude of the learner but also related to many other factors, such as teachers, curriculum, and other elements of the learning environment. Lai (2011) also affirmed that the factor that affects students’ learning motivation is reward. Rewards can increase or decrease motivation depending on the appraisal or situation in which they are presented. According to Hayikaleng et al. (2016), motivation is important because it helps students succeed in their English learning.

Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations

Deci and Ryan (1985) believed that the impact of external factors such as rewards or avoiding punishment could negatively affect learners’ learning activities. Based on their later research results, the two authors affirm that those external factors also contribute to stimulating and creating excitement and learning needs of learners. Thus, internal and external motivation plays an important role in learning. They complement and support each other to promote learning activities in learners (Deci & Ryan, 1993, p. 225).

Richard and Edward (2000, p. 55) described intrinsic and extrinsic motivation: “The most basic distinction is between Intrinsic Motivation, which refers to doing something because it is inherently interesting or interesting, and extrinsic motivation, which refers to doing something because it leads to separate outcomes”. This means that intrinsic motivation involves the learner's inner desire to do something with passion and interest in learning. Meanwhile, extrinsic motivation is related to a result or achievement as a reward for the learners.

Meanwhile, extrinsic motivation can be seen more clearly through classroom examples. In class, some students who participate in tasks may want to attract the teacher's attention. However, other students participate in class because they want to avoid being criticized by the teacher. Hayikaleng et al. (2016) determined that extrinsic motivation refers to an individual's performance to achieve rewards such as good grades or salary increases or possibly to avoid punishment. Here, students in the process of learning English are motivated by external interests, such as career opportunities, taking exams, etc. Through the above findings, intrinsic and extrinsic motivations have a special influence and interaction on second language learners. In the learning process, if there is no motivation, learning activities cannot be performed. Moreover, intrinsic motivation can be affected by external factors that hinder such as a boring learning environment or the excitement of a classroom with rewards that can motivate learners.

Instrumental and Integrative Motivations

Masgoret et al. (2003, p. 174) suggest that instrumental motivation involves practical reasons. In this study, the practical reasons mentioned are learning goals, career goals, and personal development. These practical reasons are also highlighted by another theory: “Instrumental motivation refers to the perceived pragmatic benefits of L2 proficiency and reflects the recognition that for many language learners, it is the usefulness of L2 proficiency that provides the greatest driving force to learn the language. It subsumes such utilitarian goals as receiving a better job or a higher salary due to mastering L2” (Dörnyei et al., 2006, as stated in Zanghar, 2012). This means that the instrumental motivation of learners when learning a second language is directed towards reasons such as fulfilling graduation requirements from the University, salary requirements, and practical job opportunities without interest or desire to integrate into the target language community.

Meanwhile, integrative motivation is defined as "learning a language because the learner wishes to identify with or become integrated into the society" of the target language (Gardner, 1983, p. 203). This means learning a language because one wants to "know more of the culture and values of the foreign language group... to make contact with the speakers of the languages... to live in the country concerned" (Wilkins, 1972, p. 184).

Related studies in the world

Numerous empirical studies have explored the role of motivation in language learning across various contexts. Dörnyei et al. (1998) investigated the impact of different motivational factors on English language learning among Hungarian students, finding that both integrative and instrumental motivations played a significant role in predicting language learning success.

In particular, Le (2012) researched and investigated learning motivation at the university level to determine whether motivation affects students' English learning. 290 students and seven English professors were invited to participate in the survey. The results showed that both students had extrinsic and intrinsic motivation in English subjects, but their personal learning style and the heavy curriculum affected their studies. Teachers' attitudes and perceptions about learning motivation are positive because they recognize the importance of motivation in students' English development skills.

Noemi (2014) conducted a study on learning motivation and the influence of different factors on students' learning outcomes in learning a foreign language, as well as strategies to promote students' learning motivation. The subjects of the study were a group of 20 intermediate-level business students. The study's results showed that good relationships with students are also one factor in learning motivation. Therefore, in the classroom environment, teachers provide students with adequate learning materials and create a comfortable and positive learning environment to contribute to students' learning motivation.

Another study by Al-Ta (2018) was on integrative motivation and instrumental motivation for learning English as a compulsory requirement in college. The subjects of the study were 50 second-year students studying English communication skills of various majors. The questionnaire used to collect data and the integrative and instrumental measures were adapted from Gardner's (1985) learning attitudes and motivation. The study results showed that students were highly motivated in the context of integrative and instrumental motivation. However, their instrumental motivation was more substantial than integrative motivation. The researcher suggested creating a positive classroom environment that motivates and encourages learners to participate actively in classroom activities.

Batubara et al. (2020) conducted a gender-based study to assess motivation to learn English as a foreign language. They found that different factors influence motivation to learn, namely empowerment, usefulness, success and interest. They show that female students experience these positive factors to a lesser extent than male students. They concluded that teachers need to create a learning environment where these elements are shared by all students and especially for female students and low-achieving students.

Related studies in Vietnam

Nguyen (2015) researched and investigated methods to motivate students who are not significant in English. The research method is a combination of qualitative and quantitative. Quantitative data is a survey questionnaire for 60 students from Hanoi University of Education 2 and 60 from the University of Education. Qualitative data is interviews with ten teachers, including 5 Vietnamese teachers and 5 English teachers. The investigation found three main issues: non-professional students' motivation to learn English comes from career and communication opportunities. Teachers play an essential role in increasing students' motivation. Finally, the cause of reduced learning motivation is not setting clear personal goals.

According to a study by Pham (2016), special emphasis was placed on cultural factors that contribute to students' motivation in learning English as a second language in high school. From the results, they showed that encouragement from parents, peer influence and awareness of achieving personal goals play important roles in students' motivation to learn English as a second language.

Ngo et al. (2017) researched the motivation to learn English as a second language between English majors and non-English majors. They used a quantitative design to evaluate different types of motivation. They discovered that both groups of subjects were highly motivated to learn English because they needed it to prepare for their future careers. These students were intrinsically motivated and promoted their existing intrinsic motivation in learning English.

Nguyen (2019) studied English language learning motivation among students at the University of Technology, Vietnam National University, Hanoi, focusing on two main types of motivation: instrumental and intrinsic. The evaluation and comparison results showed that instrumental motivation promotes learning more than intrinsic motivation. This tendency is because most students want to become proficient in English to meet job requirements, have a good job, or meet the school's foreign language requirements. In addition, according to this study, parents also play a role in creating motivation for students to learn English. Students whose parents can speak English also have higher motivation to learn than others. The importance of parents' attitudes, motivations, and behavior in learning was entirely consistent with the views of previous studies. It can be said that instrumental motivation plays a significant role in students' learning motivation.

Recently, Khau and Thach (2021) researched whether students learning English are motivated to learn. This study focuses on extrinsic motivation to see what factors help students stay motivated to learn. The research method is quantitative, with a survey questionnaire created and distributed to 52 students studying 3rd and 4th years majoring in English to participate in the survey.

Research results show that learning motivation is related to learning facilities and teacher personality. These two factors help students think positively and be motivated during language learning.

Although numerous studies have examined language learning motivation, there is limited research specifically addressing the English learning motivation of non-English major students at Nguyen Tat Thanh University. Most previous studies have focused on English majors or general educational contexts, overlooking the career-driven motivations and the unique learning environment of non-English majors at this university. These studies predominantly emphasize common factors such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, without delving deeply into the specific motivations linked to career aspirations often pursued by non-English major students. Additionally, the learning environment at the researched university, which integrates internationally oriented programs and diverse major-specific courses, creates unique factors that influence the learning motivation of non-English majors. Thus, this study aims at exploring the English learning motivations of this group, particularly in understanding how extrinsic factors such as career opportunities, learning environment, and teaching methods impact their motivation to learn.

FACTORS INFLUENCING MOTIVATION

The role of the teacher

Many studies agree that teachers are one of the essential factors affecting learners' motivation to learn. Ramage (1990) pointed out that teachers should try to make students participate in the learning process, which can influence students' motivation to achieve their goals.

Oxford and Shearin (1994) pointed out five points where teachers can motivate their students: encourage students to achieve goals actively; face challenges to achieve their goals; help students realize the benefits of learning languages; create a lively, friendly learning environment; most importantly, encourage students' intrinsic motivation to help them have exciting experiences during the learning process.

According to another study by Batubara et al. (2020), they conducted a gender-based study to assess motivation to learn English as a foreign language. They found that different factors influence learning motivation: empowerment, usefulness, success, and interest. They concluded that teachers need to create a learning environment where these elements are shared by all students, especially female and low-achieving students.

Teachers are a significant factor in motivating students throughout the learning process. In the classroom, many students feel anxious and lack confidence. Teachers promptly monitor, observe, encourage, and encourage students to motivate and help students actively participate in class. Teachers also create a fun and friendly learning atmosphere, motivating students to attend class fully.

Teaching Methods and Classroom Environment

Dörnyei (2001) proposed that teachers can motivate students by applying many exciting strategies. It is essential to create a relaxing and friendly classroom atmosphere. Vibulphol (2016) has shown the role of teachers' motivational strategies in enhancing students' intrinsic motivation to learn English inside and outside the classroom.

In addition, classroom layout and teaching equipment are also factors that affect students' learning motivation.

The framework of the study

Below is a diagram to illustrate the study of learning motivation within the context of the provided theories

Figure 1: Structural diagram of study on learning motivation.

This layout presents the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, their respective factors, conclusions, and primary influences. It helps to summarize the research findings and identify the key factors contributing to each type of motivation.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted to determine the motivational orientations of non-English major second-year students at a private university in Ho Chi Minh City and the factors that influence their motivation of learning English. This study used a mixed-methods design. The number of participants was 200, and 10 participants were randomly selected for an in-depth interview. For the interviews, the purposive sampling technique was a small group of students willing to participate and chose the language of convenience. The selection criteria included students who showed different motivation levels in the survey, ensuring the interviews could explore various experiences and attitudes towards learning English. The purposive sampling method ensured that the participants provided information about their language learning motivation.

This study was carried out to find out the answers for the research questions:

- 1) What motivation do second-year non-English major students aim to achieve with English learning at this university?
- 2) What practical and effective suggestions can be proposed to improve the learning motivation of second-year non-English major students at this university?

Data collection

In this study, data were collected through online surveys and small group interviews to ensure the comprehensiveness and representativeness of the research sample.

A survey was designed on Google Forms, including questions related to students' motivation to learn English. The survey was divided into 3 main parts: the first part collected demographic information such as gender, age, and major; the second part included Likert-type questions to assess intrinsic and extrinsic motivation; and the last part included open-ended questions to collect students' personal opinions.

First, we had the consent of the university management to visit the classrooms to collect research data, including direct interviews and sending the survey link to the students.

The survey link was sent via email or zalo to 350 students. They were required to complete the survey within two weeks. After the survey period ended, a total of 300 responses were collected. Of these, 200 valid responses, which fully met the research participation criteria as initially determined, were selected for analysis.

In addition to the survey, a small group interview of 10 students from different majors such as Medical Physics, Business Administration, Biomedical Engineering, Nursing, and Automotive Technology was conducted. The interviews were recorded with the consent of the participating students and the data from the interviews were used to supplement the survey results, helping to enhance the reliability and comprehensiveness of the study.

The collected data has been encrypted and securely stored to ensure confidentiality and will only be used for research purposes.

4. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Firstly, an overview of basic information of the participants in the study was shown. Figure 2 shows the sample distribution in terms of majors: 28% are in automotive technology, 22.5% are in nursing, and the rest are in other fields of which the majors in the sample are predominantly technical.

Figure 2. Distribution of majors in the study

Descriptive Statistical Analysis of the data

We conducted a descriptive statistical analysis of the observed variables, separating them into intrinsic and extrinsic motivation groups. Descriptive statistical analysis provides detailed information on the characteristics of each variable group, including mean

values, standard deviations, and other indicators. This helps me better interpret the level and distribution of each motivation type in the student's English learning process. The descriptive statistical analysis includes the following steps: (1) Descriptive statistical analysis of the observed variables belonging to the internal motivation group; (2) Descriptive statistical analysis of the observed variables belonging to the external motivation group; (3) Compare and collate the influence level of the external factors on the English learning process.

Data of the observed variables belonging to intrinsic motivation factors are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Intrinsic Motivation

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
IM1- I find learning English to be an enjoyable experience.	200	1	5	4.17	1.049
IM2- I feel motivated to learn English because I believe it will improve my cognitive abilities.	200	1	5	4.21	.968
IM3 - I engage in activities that allow me to practice my English skills outside of the classroom.	200	1	5	3.97	1.072
IM4 - I believe that having English proficiency will give me access to broader knowledge.	200	1	5	4.36	.924
IM5 - I believe that my own self-discipline is a factor in my motivation to learn English.	200	1	5	4.26	.931
IM6 - I believe that my own learning style influences my motivation to learn English.	200	1	5	4.19	.958
IM7- I find that I learn English more effectively when I am motivated.	200	1	5	4.38	.905
IM8- My motivation to learn English helps me to overcome obstacles and challenges.	200	1	5	4.24	.973
IM9- My motivation to learn English has helped me to persist through difficult or frustrating periods.	200	1	5	4.15	1.024
IM10- I find that I am more willing to invest time and effort into learning English when I am motivated.	200	1	5	4.22	.941
IM11- I believe that my motivation to learn English has helped me to make progress more quickly.	200	1	5	4.24	.943
Valid N (listwise)	200				

The mean values of the questions ranged from 3.97 to 4.38, indicating that most students had a fairly high level of agreement with the statements related to intrinsic motivation in learning English. This suggests that students primarily perceive learning English as a positive experience and are motivated to learn.

IM4 – “I believe that having English proficiency will give me access to broader knowledge” has a mean value of 4.36, one of the highest values, showing that students are very confident that English proficiency will expand their knowledge. This reflects a personal motivation to learn English and a future vision regarding knowledge.

IM7 – “I find that I learn English more effectively when I am motivated” has the highest mean value of 4.38, demonstrating that students feel personal motivation greatly affects their effectiveness in learning English.

IM3 – “I engage in activities that allow me to practice my English skills outside of the classroom” has the lowest mean value of 3.97, indicating that some students may not be actively participating in extracurricular activities to practice their English skills or they may lack opportunities to do so.

Standard Deviation

The standard deviation ranges from 0.905 to 1.072, indicating that the level of dispersion in the responses is relatively low to moderate, meaning most students tend to respond similarly.

IM7 has the lowest standard deviation of 0.905, showing high consistency in responses regarding the belief that motivation helps them learn English more effectively. This can be interpreted as most students agreeing that when they are motivated, they learn English better.

IM3 has the highest standard deviation of 1.072, indicating a significant difference among students regarding their participation in activities outside the classroom to practice English. This may reflect disparities in opportunities or self-learning capabilities among students.

Overall, the questions related to intrinsic motivation show high mean values, indicating that students have a strong motivation to learn English. Factors related to improving personal skills, future aspirations, and learning effectiveness when motivated are prominent. However, practicing English skills outside the classroom may be an area where many students encounter difficulties or lack motivation.

Table 2 provides descriptive statistics for the external motivation variables related to students' motivation to learn English. These statistics were derived from 200 respondents and reflect various external factors influencing their motivation. Each variable is rated on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). This section analyzes the survey data related to extrinsic motivation, focusing on the external factors that influence students' motivation to learn English. The descriptive statistics for the 13 observed variables provide insights into how external pressures, opportunities, and environments affect students' English learning motivation.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Extrinsic Motivation

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
M1- I feel motivated to learn English because I want to communicate with English speakers.	200	1	5	4.18	1.034
EM2- I feel motivated to learn English because it will help me achieve my personal goals.	200	1	5	4.31	.948
EM3- Pressure from friends is a motivation for me to learn English.	200	1	5	3.71	1.234
EM4- Requirements of favorite job should learn English.	200	1	5	4.08	1.034
EM5- Academic Results, Scholarships, Grades	200	1	5	4.07	1.108
EM6- Learning English is important for my future career prospects.	200	1	5	4.36	.924
EM7- I think that having English proficiency will increase my chances of getting a better job.	200	1	5	4.45	.861
EM8- Having English proficiency will lead to a higher salary in my profession.	200	1	5	4.47	.856

EM9- English proficiency can open up various job opportunities for me in the future.	200	1	5	4.43	.916
EM10- I believe that the quality of English language instruction influences my motivation to learn.	200	1	5	4.25	.996
EM11- I believe that the support and encouragement of others influences my motivation to learn English.	200	1	5	4.12	.982
EM12- I find that I am more motivated to learn English when I see the practical benefits of doing so.	200	1	5	4.27	.935
EM13- Learning in a relaxed and encouraging environment can significantly improve my language memory.	200	1	5	4.29	.959
Valid N (listwise)	200				

It can be seen from the Table that proficiency in English is linked to higher salaries. The low standard deviation suggests that most students share this belief, reflecting a clear understanding of the economic benefits of English skills.

EM7 – “I think that having English proficiency will increase my chances of getting a better job.”. This factor shows a high mean value and low standard deviation, indicating a strong consensus on the connection between English proficiency and job opportunities. Students feel that English is essential for career advancement. EM6 – “Learning English is important for my future career prospects” whose Mean was 4.36 and Standard Deviation was 0.924. This factor also has a high mean value, demonstrating that students recognize the importance of English in shaping their future careers. The relatively low standard deviation indicates consistent responses among students.

On the other hands, EM3 - "Pressure from friends is a motivation for me to learn English" has the lowest mean value, indicating that peer pressure is not a significant motivating factor for most students. The high standard deviation reflects substantial variation in responses, suggesting that some students feel peer pressure strongly, while others do not see it as a motivator at all. EM1 – “I feel motivated to learn English because I want to communicate with English speakers" with the Standard Deviation of 1.034 indicates a moderate level of variability in responses, suggesting that while many students find communication with English speakers motivating, others do not prioritize this reason as highly. EM4 – “Requirements of favorite job should learn English” with the Standard Deviation of 1.034 indicates varied opinions regarding job requirements as a motivation for learning English. Some students see this as essential, while others may not feel the same urgency.

In a nutshell, the high standard deviations in factors EM1, EM3, EM4, and EM5 indicate significant variability in student motivations and perceptions, reflecting diverse experiences and influences. In contrast, the low standard deviations in factors EM7, EM8, and EM9 demonstrate strong consensus among students regarding the economic advantages of English proficiency, highlighting a shared understanding of its importance in career advancement.

The descriptive statistical analysis of extrinsic motivation reveals that external factors such as career prospects, salary expectations, and job opportunities are significant motivators for students learning English. The data shows a strong agreement on the importance of English proficiency for future success, with most variables having high mean scores and relatively low standard deviations. However, factors like peer pressure and academic performance show more variation in their influence on student motivation, reflecting a diverse range of experiences and perceptions among the students.

The analysis shows that extrinsic motivational factors, such as career advancement and financial rewards, have a significantly stronger impact on students' English learning motivation than intrinsic factors. Specifically, students rated the impact of English proficiency on getting a higher salary with an average score of 4.47 and getting better job opportunities with an average score of 4.45. The strong emphasis on financial and career-related motivations suggests that these extrinsic rewards are the main motivators for students.

Intrinsic motivation, including personal enjoyment of learning English and self-discipline, also influenced students' motivation but to a lesser extent. The mean score of intrinsic motivation was 4.22, which was slightly lower than the mean score of 4.23 for extrinsic motivation. This shows that although students value internal reasons for learning English, such as personal growth and interest, these reasons are less attractive than external rewards such as career opportunities and financial benefits. Therefore, the data shows that extrinsic motivations have a greater influence on students' motivation to learn English.

The analysis data also shows that extrinsic motivation factors show higher consistency among students. The responses are more uniform, indicating that students broadly agree on the importance of extrinsic rewards such as career benefits and financial benefits. This consistency highlights that most students consider these practical benefits to be important motivators.

Meanwhile, intrinsic motivation factors show greater variability. This variability reflects a wider range of personal reasons for learning English, such as enjoyment and self-improvement, which are more subjective and varied. The differences in responses to intrinsic motivation suggest that personal motivation is less uniform than the more widely recognized extrinsic rewards.

The data clearly indicate that extrinsic motivation, particularly related to career advancement and financial gain, has a more significant and consistent influence on students' motivation to learn English than intrinsic motivation. While personal interest and self-efficacy play an important role, they are overshadowed by the attractive extrinsic rewards associated with language proficiency. The analysis suggests that students are more strongly motivated by the practical benefits of learning English, such as better job opportunities and higher salaries, rather than by personal enjoyment or intrinsic growth.

The results of the EFA analysis confirmed that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors significantly influenced students' English learning process. Intrinsic motivation includes factors such as enjoyment in learning English (IM1) and the belief that English proficiency will expand their knowledge (IM4). These are self-generated factors within each individual, often related to personal satisfaction and joy in learning. This is consistent with the intrinsic motivation theory of Ryan and Deci (2002), in which learners feel autonomous and self-determined in their learning process. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation includes factors such as the desire to communicate with English speakers (EM1) and peer pressure (EM3). These factors are driven by external influences, such as future job requirements or the desire to achieve good academic results. This supports Deci and Ryan's (1985) extrinsic motivation theory, in which learning behavior is motivated by rewards or avoidance of negative consequences.

The descriptive statistics show that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation have a strong influence on students' English learning, with high mean values for both types of motivation (MeanIM = 4.22 and MeanEM = 4.23). This suggests that students are not only motivated by external factors, such as achieving personal goals (EM2), but also by personal satisfaction and learning enjoyment (IM1).

The influence of external factors, especially increased career opportunities (EM7) and increased salary (EM8), is rated highest among the external factors. This is consistent with Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, in which the expectation of external rewards and the perception of practical benefits can be strong motivators.

The findings of this study are fully consistent with the theoretical frameworks proposed in the previous part. According to Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2002), both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation play an important role in promoting learning behavior. This study demonstrates that students have strong intrinsic motivation, such as believing in the value of learning English, and extrinsic motivation, such as the desire to achieve career success.

In addition, the results also show that social and environmental factors influence students' learning motivation, which is consistent with the theories of Bandura (1977) and Dörnyei (2001). Factors such as support from others (EM11) and a comfortable learning environment (EM13) are highly rated by students, indicating that not only students themselves but also social factors play an important role in the learning process.

In summary, the results of this study confirmed the importance of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in motivating students to learn English. Factors such as learning enjoyment, external pressure, and practical benefits were shown to be the main motivators

that help students overcome challenges in their learning process. This not only supports existing motivational theories but also provides empirical evidence to better understand language learning motivation in the context of today's students.

Analysis of the survey data revealed that the majority of second-year non-English major students at NTTU recognized the significant impact of motivation on their English learning process. The findings indicated that students were aware of how motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, influenced their language learning ability..

Interestingly, the results show that external motivation factors have a slightly higher level of agreement among students compared to internal motivation factors, with mean values of 4.2296 and 4.2168, respectively. This suggests that external motivation plays a crucial role in driving students' learning efforts. Students are particularly aware of how English proficiency can enhance their career prospects, increase income potential, and contribute to personal development.

The exploratory factor analysis (EFA) highlights the importance of English in achieving career and personal goals, as well as the influence of social and external factors on students' motivation. Based on these findings, the study recommends that English language teaching programs should focus on creating a positive learning environment that integrates practical benefits and external support to further boost student motivation.

The study also highlighted that extrinsic motivation has a strong impact on students' motivation to learn English at NTTU. This finding is consistent with the reality of the current educational and social context, where external factors significantly influence students' learning environment and motivation. While intrinsic motivation - derived from individual perception, effort, and motivation - remains important, the current educational context also requires attention to extrinsic motivation. Factors such as classroom environment, teaching methods, and career opportunities positively influence students' willingness to study. High salaries and promising career prospects, as well as the appeal of scholarships and awards, continuously influence students, strengthening their internal motivation and helping them maintain a strong and consistent drive to succeed.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the study results the following recommendations may be carried out to improve student's learning motivation.

❖ For the university management: Based on the survey results, external motivation substantially impacts students' ability to maintain their learning motivation. The university should create a positive, friendly, and attractive learning environment. A comfortable learning space with bright colors will help students relax when participating in class. The university needs to build a close and friendly educational environment, and students always receive prompt and timely support from school staff to feel secure in their learning process.

In addition, the study also shows that students want to practice English skills outside the classroom. The school needs more extracurricular activities to attract students to participate and practice speaking skills, such as establishing an English club. This English club can take place on weekends, and students who participate will be credited with their practice points to increase their motivation. This club is where students only use English to communicate, and there are discussions on each topic for the participating students. This is like a playground where students can practice their listening and speaking skills and create bonds between class members. In order to avoid incurring many costs, this English club can be considered a speaking practice session in the curriculum, and teachers can consider adjusting to help students have more practice opportunities. Based on this study, students believe studying English should help them gain a better income, a better career, and a higher chance of promotion. We can utilize this result to promote a benefit for students who can use English well. For example, agreements can be made with firms seeking candidates who are good in English to provide scholarships or internships. Extracurricular activities to encourage the use of English that can result in their GPA or CV can also be considered. We can also encourage students to learn English through scholarships or rewards. Furthermore, students with particular success in studying English should be promoted to raise awareness and motivation among other students.

❖ For teachers: From the survey results, the learning environment and teaching methods positively impact student motivation. Therefore, we need to innovate in teaching methods. In today's learning environment, the role of the learner has become central, opening up many opportunities to innovate educational methods. Teachers are not only the ones who impart knowledge, but they also have many positive impacts on student motivation, helping students develop skills and independent thinking during the learning process. This emphasizes that the responsibility of teachers does not stop at disseminating information; They are essential in creating rich and stimulating learning experiences for their students. Through support, encouragement, and constructive feedback,

teachers can help students overcome challenges and develop skills with greater confidence. In doing so, they support the learning process and foster confidence in each student's abilities. Or the integration of technology into the teaching process, especially in the context of learners facing limitations in daily interactions with language. This positive change in teaching methods and approaches will impact students and help them feel more interested in the classroom environment.

❖ For students: The survey results in the study analyzed that external motivation affects students more than internal motivation, but intrinsic motivation is also essential. External support will not be effective if students do not try, do not have their own goals, do not participate in classroom activities, or do not meet the requirements set by the school. Therefore, while still in school, students should study hard, participate in class actively and proactively, and persevere with their goals. Students should set clear personal goals and understand the benefits of learning a language to maintain their internal motivation and make learning more enjoyable and accessible.

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